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INDIVIDUAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SPECIALISTS OF PRIMARY TACTICAL FIRE AND RESCUE UNITS SES OF UKRAINE

In article analyzes the individual psychological characteristics of specialists of primary tactical fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine and being determined features of subjective factors that lead to the formation of a feel of cohesion.

Keywords: activism, solidarity, combined unit, groups, psychological compatibility, individual psychological characteristics, the primary tactical fire and rescue units.

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ИНДИВІДУАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ФАХІВЦІВ ПЕРВИННИХ ТАКТИЧНИХ ПОЖЕЖНО-РЯТУВАЛЬНИХ ПІДРОЗДІЛІВ ДСНС УКРАЇНИ

Стаття присвячена аналізу індивідуально-психологічних особливостей фахівців первинних тактичних пожежно-рятувальних підрозділів ДСНС України та визначенню суб'єктивних чинників, які обумовлюють формування відчуття згуртованості.

Ключеві слова: діяльність, згуртованість, зведений загін, групи, психологічна сумісність, індивідуально-психологічні особливості, первинні тактичні пожежно-рятувальні підрозділи.

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ИНДИВІДУАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ПЕРВИЧНЫХ ТАКТИЧЕСКИХ ПОЖАРНО-СПАСАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПОДРАЗДЕЛЕНИЙ ГСЧС УКРАИНЫ

Статья посвящена анализу индивидуально-психологических особенностей специалистов первичных тактических пожарно-спасательных подразделений ГСЧС Украины и определению субъективных факторов, обуславливающих формирование чувства сплоченности.

Ключевые слова: деятельность, сплоченность, сводный отряд, группы, психологическая совместимость, индивидуально-психологические особенности, первичные тактические пожарно-спасательные подразделения.

Formulation of the problem. Activities of the State Emergency Service of Ukraine (SES of Ukraine), unlike many other professions, is related with conditions of permanent extremality: the responsibility for the life and health of personnel; ensuring the technical readiness of equipment; high temperature and concentration of combustion products; the work at height; considerable physical loading during rescue people and valuable property etc.

We must also accent attention on the insufficient number of fire and rescue appliances and equipment of Ukrainian fire departments, low level of social and medical protection of workers in this field. This list can still continue, but the result of all the above circumstances is the problem of ensuring adequate professional and psychological readiness of personnel [1; 2; 9].

Analysis of recent research and publications. The analysis of the scientific literature shows that in the national psychology among of a number of psychological research various aspects of workers of professions related to the risk (professional and psychological deformation, occupational stress, social and psychological foundations of mental health preservation, individual adaptation to the special conditions of activity, and psychological characteristics and determinants of suicide, industrial traumatism, professional selection, psychological training, syndrome of "burnout", behavioral strategies for coping of stress in a professional activity, forecasting of professional dependability etc.), questions of specifics of professional activity primary tactical fire-rescue units was paid a little attention [4].

Setting objectives. The study of psychological compatibility of specialists of primary tactical fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine requires a gradual solution of many practical problems. One of these problems is, in our view, is determining factors causing psychological compatibility firefighters. Among these factors, one of the leading position occupy a individual-psychological characteristics of everyone member of the unit.

We assume that the study of psychological qualities of firefighters will able to get a detailed picture of their impact on the degree of psychological compatibility.

Presenting of main material. To implement our plan, from the total number of personnel that is part of the primary tactical fire-rescue units of Main Departments (MD) SES of Ukraine in Kharkiv and Dnipro regions, we have selected and tested 187 rescuers. Investigated firefighters were distributed in this manner:

- **joint detachment** – 105 firefighters aged 26 to 44 years. Length of service in SES of Ukraine from 1 to 20 years. United in a large unit to performing tasks of emergencies response and extinguishing large fires. They all have one professional purpose (set by management). They are unfamiliar

with each other. Selected from different departments of MD SES of Ukraine in Dnipro region (see Table. 1).

When performing service tasks were integrated randomly into 3 groups on the nature of the performed service tasks:

1st group – composed 30 firefighters aged 27 to 39 years;

2nd group – comprised of 42 firefighters aged 26 to 42 years;

3rd group – composed of 33 firefighters aged 28 to 44 years.

Specialists of these three groups have performed complex tasks in the territory of the Dnipro region (see Table 1).

- So-called “**comparison unit**”, consisting of:

1st group – 48 firefighters MD SES of Ukraine in Kharkiv region aged 24 to 45 years. Length of service in SES of Ukraine from 1 to 15 years. It is a professional group whose members are familiar with each other for at least 1 month. They differ from other high level of psychological compatibility;

2nd group – 34 firefighters PG SES of Ukraine in Kharkiv region aged 24 to 41 years. Length of service in SES of Ukraine from 1 to 16 year.

The subjects that are included in the “comparison unit” stand in our investigation as standards of comparison or control group. This helped us to identify the factors that cause psychological compatibility and predict its level on the example specially created professional groups (joint detachment).

Table 1

Information on the activities of the joint unit № 1 (Dnipro city)

Name of joint unit	Date and place (the object) of the joint unit during extinguishing fires	Fire appliance						Quantity of personnel that were involved
		basic		special		supporting		
		mark	quantity	mark	quantity	mark	quantity	
Joint unit № 1, Dnipro city	20.10.2014 peat fire village Balivka	TLF-40(53228) 40(43252)247.0 2		FPS- 110 FH-2	1 1			45
	1.08.2014 forest fire near the urban villages Cherkaske	TLF -40(53228) 40(43252)247.0 2 TLF -40(130) TLF -40(131)	1 1 1 2					60

At baseline, we have studied and analyzed the major individual-psychological quality of firefighters who formed the control group. This

procedure was carried out in order to highlight a number of personality traits that may cause the psychological compatibility with other members of the unit.

In subsequently results were compared with the demonstration of psychological qualities of firefighters who took part in the aftermath of the peat fire in the village Balivka and forest fire near the urban village Cherkaske of Dnipro region.

Comparison of feature of personality factors of firefighters of primary fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine with different levels of psychological compatibility (“comparison unit”) helped to determine a number of significant differences (see Table 2 and Fig. 1).

Table 2

Expression of individual-psychological features of specialists of primary fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine with different level of psychological compatibility (“comparison unit”)

Factor	1st group of “comparison unit” (M ±m)	2nd group of “comparison unit” (M ±m)	t	p
A	7,06 ±0,56	4,96 ±0,39	3,08**	0,01
B	5,58± 0,30	5,51± 0,33	0,23	-
C	7,17 ±0,21	6,49 ±0,69	1,39	-
E	5,11 ±0,19	7,20 ±0,26	2,34*	0,05
F	6,39 ±0,29	6,46± 0,44	0,39	-
G	8,94± 0,33	7,86 ±0,30	1,99	-
H	5,76± 0,28	5,48±0,47	1,05	-
I	6,70± 0,65	4,66 ±0,48	2,61*	0,05
L	3,89 ±0,21	5,08± 0,49	2,17*	0,05
M	5,79 ±0,45	4,36± 0,27	1,36	-
N	7,56 ±0,77	4,94 ±0,30	2,15*	0,05
O	5,27± 0,25	4,17 ±0,37	1,08	-
Q1	7,97± 0,41	5,30 ±0,41	1,87	-
Q2	4,31 ±0,67	5,06 ±0,54	1,35	-
Q3	8,15 ±0,78	5,36 ±0,37	3,07*	0,05
Q4	5,17 ±0,65	4,30± 0,29	1,60	-

Firefighters of the first group (high level of psychological compatibility) differ from their colleagues from the second group of higher level of sociability - personality factor "A". Results are reliable at the level of $p \leq 0,01$. So the firefighters from the first group can be described as open-minded for

cooperation, more attentive to their colleagues and to their interests. These experts can easily install and maintain social contacts. Such personalities are seeking social confirmation and require support and recognition of their actions. Accordingly, the firefighters which belong to second group, often suffer from difficulties in interpersonal relations and when establishing contacts with others.

Fig. 1. Profiles of personality firefighters of 1st and 2nd groups SES of Ukraine with different rates of psychological compatibility (“comparison unit”).

The next reliable differences were observed regarding the expressivity of personal factor "E» ($t = 2,34$, at $p \leq 0,05$). Established that the firefighters of SES of Ukraine, which belong to the second group, unlike their colleagues, characterized by the dominance, the independence, focusing on their personality. These specialists also tend to show signs of authoritarian behavior, stubbornness and want to be a leader.

These experts believe its only true point of view, and prefer to public recognition. Therefore we can assume that the listed individual psychological characteristics may adversely affect the process of establishing a positive psychological climate in the unit and interfere with the formation of group cohesion.

A similar trend was recorded concerning expression of factor «L», which is more pronounced in firefighters of the second group ($t = 2,17$, at $p \leq 0,05$).

This personalities factor describes the emotional relationship of the personality to other people. So firefighters from the first group differ by the openness, tolerance for peculiarity of others. In some cases, they tend to demonstrate conformism. Employees of the second group of "comparison unit" by contrast, is cautious in social contact, prone to jealousy. These specialists often seek to avoid responsibility for errors, while trying to be independent and self-reliant.

It was also found that firefighters from the second group, in contrast to their colleagues from the first group of "comparison unit" are more stringent rational and logical in their actions. They almost do not tend to show their feelings and emotions and show empathy. Differences are reliable at the level $p \leq 0,05$.

The results show that the personality factor «N» authentically higher in group 1 employees primary fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine ($t = 2,15$, at $p \leq 0,05$). This suggests that these firefighters in communicating more diplomatic, emotionally restrained, careful and tactful. These results make it possible to characterize the firefighters from the first group "comparing unit" as disciplined, purposeful professionals who can sometimes change the emotionality to the hardness and the sincerity to the suspicion. Specialists second group "comparison unit" can be slow when performing group activities, hinder the adoption of joint solutions and show uncertainty in their rationality, and so on.

Last significant difference in severity of personal factors were recorded concerning indication factor «Q₃», which characterizes the level of self-control of personality. It was found that firefighters of first group different from their counterparts from the second group of "comparison unit" have higher level of self-control. This quality is very important in interpersonal communication and interaction with others. So firefighters of first group "comparison unit" inherent purposefulness, ability to control their emotions and behavior. They prone to organizing activities and work effectively in high stressors. These professionals usually take an active stance in solution of problems of unit.

Received reliable differences in the expression of personality factors of firefighters with different grade psychological compatibility indicate that the dominant qualities it is personality traits that are directly related to the sphere of interpersonal relationships and in some way responsible for their quality.

The next step of our research was to study individual-psychological characteristics of specialists-firefighters of three groups of joint detachment that took part in the aftermath of the peat fire in the village Balivka and forest fire near the urban village Cherkaske of Dnipro region and comparison their results with data the study of personality's qualities of firefighters from "comparison unit". The data are presented in tables 3-6 and in Fig. 2.

A comparative analysis of expression data on individual-psychological qualities of employees of primary fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine, which belong to the first group of joint detachment, and were obtained next results. It is established that such personal factors as the level of sociability - "A" and the level of emotional stability - "C" - are less distinct in the first group of joint detachment, rather than employees of the first group of "comparison unit » (t = 2 88, at p≤0,05 and t = 2,06, at p≤0,05 respectively).

We can say that firefighters of first team from joint unit is differ that they have difficulties in establishing interpersonal contacts, reticence, focuses on self. At the same time, these specialists emotionally unstable, they often change mood, they tend to change the interests and principles. Maybe the marked qualities causing the emergence of each other and affect the quality of psychological compatibility of this professionals with other members of the unit.

Table 3

Comparative characteristic expression of personal factors in firefighters of first, second and third groups of joint unit

Factor	1st group of joint unit (M ±m)	2nd group of joint unit (M ±m)	3rd group of joint unit (M ±m)	t (1, 2)	t (1, 3)	t (2, 3)
A	4,98 ±0,15	8,66 ±0,38	5,95 ±0,40	3,84**	1,23	2,90*
B	5,39± 0,28	6,94± 0,53	6,74 ±0,67	1,39	1,03	0,35
C	5,97 ±0,23	7,49 ±0,40	6,08± 0,26	1,89	1,19	1,07
E	5,69 ±0,49	6,28 ±0,96	6,39 ±0,46	1,18	1,44	0,49
F	6,87 ±0,39	6,02± 0,48	6,22 ±0,17	0,48	0,22	0,56
G	6,94± 0,25	7,06 ±0,32	7,59± 0,32	1,03	1,46	0,32
H	6,36± 0,18	6,99 ±0,57	5,77 ±0,26	0,71	1,58	1,91
I	6,70± 0,24	5,66 ±0,40	4,85± 0,31	2,01*	2,40*	1,29
L	5,09 ±0,27	5,00± 0,49	6,70± 0,31	0,07	1,43	1,54
M	5,39 ±0,28	4,77± 0,24	4,44± 0,86	1,22	1,13	0,05
N	5,38 ±0,76	6,95 ±0,16	6,47± 0,43	2,07*	1,58	0,43
O	5,20± 0,35	4,57 ±0,33	3,75 ±0,35	1,05	1,88	1,35
Q1	4,40± 0,31	5,54 ±0,42	5,04± 0,37	1,09	1,16	0,55
Q2	4,77 ±0,39	5,46 ±0,45	4,89 ±0,32	1,41	0,17	1,70
Q3	6,15 ±0,22	6,46 ±0,47	5,48 ±0,73	0,15	1,06	1,13
Q4	5,89±0,78	4,35± 0,39	4,97± 0,46	1,22	1,43	0,72

«*» – p ≤ 0,05; «**» – p ≤ 0,01

Fig. 2. Profiles of personality of employees of primary fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine, which joined to the temporarily generated joint unit.

A similar trend was recorded in respect of expression of personal factor «G», which indicators are significantly lower than in the first studied group of joint unit ($t = 2,09$, at $p \leq 0,05$). This factor characterizes the normative of behavior of the personality - namely its level.

Thus, the results indicate that employees in primary fire-rescue units that belong to the first group, can state disposition for changes in behavior, disorganization, irresponsibility. These specialists do not always follow the general group norms and rules what practically not acceptable in professional careers SES of Ukraine. In addition, this personal factor indicates the features emotional-volitional sphere of personality and, in this case, help to determine weak points in the first group firefighters of the joint unit.

In addition to the above, experts first group of joint unit, unlike their colleagues in the first group of "comparison unit" tend to treat others cautiously. They prefer to be more self-reliant and independent. Such personalities differ egocentrism and a penchant for competition ($t = 2,04$ at $p \leq 0,05$).

In addition, it was found that in the first group of joint unit is significantly lower severity of personal factors «N» and «Q1». Results are valid at level $p \leq 0,05$.

Table 4

Comparative characteristic expression of personal factors in employees of "comparison unit" and the firefighters of first group of joint unit

Factor	1st group of "comparison unit" (M ±m)	2nd group of "comparison unit" (M ±m)	1st group of joint unit (M ±m)	t (1 c.u., 1 joint unit)	t (2 c.u., 1 joint unit)
A	7,06 ±0,56	4,96 ±0,39	4,98 ±0,15	2,88*	0,07
B	5,58± 0,30	5,51± 0,33	5,39± 0,28	1,03	0,94
C	7,17 ±0,21	6,49 ±0,69	5,97 ±0,23	2,06*	1,62
E	5,11 ±0,19	7,20 ±0,26	5,69 ±0,49	0,45	1,78
F	6,39 ±0,29	6,46± 0,44	6,87 ±0,39	0,75	0,32
G	8,94± 0,33	7,86 ±0,30	6,94± 0,25	2,09*	1,37
H	5,76± 0,28	5,48 ±0,47	6,36± 0,18	1,72	1,80
I	6,70± 0,65	4,66 ±0,48	6,70± 0,24	-	1,69
L	3,89 ±0,21	5,08± 0,49	5,09 ±0,27	2,04*	0,17
M	5,79 ±0,45	4,36± 0,27	5,39 ±0,28	1,28	1,55
N	7,56 ±0,77	4,94 ±0,30	5,38 ±0,76	2,25*	1,46
O	5,27± 0,25	4,17 ±0,37	5,20± 0,35	0,57	1,33
Q1	7,97± 0,41	5,30 ±0,41	4,40± 0,31	2,80*	1,41
Q2	4,31 ±0,67	5,06 ±0,54	4,77±0,39	0,67	1,34
Q3	8,15 ±0,78	5,36 ±0,37	6,15 ±0,22	1,90	1,23
Q4	5,17 ±0,65	4,30± 0,29	5,89±0,78	1,17	1,62

«*» – $p \leq 0,05$

So firefighters which belong to the first group of joint unit differ of sincerity in his actions and in communication with others, often showing indecisiveness and conservatism. These specialists often criticize new ideas and methods at solving professional problems. It characteristically to them to fear a changes in every sphere of life.

Mentioned individual-psychological characteristics of the employees of fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine, which belong to the first group of joint unit, allow to assume the fact that the level of psychological compatibility in this group will be low, as most specialists are differ in focused on their personality and characterized by general indecision to changes.

From this we can assume that these specialists in the performance of joint professional activity in the unit would show not very high professional results.

Table 5

Comparative characteristic expression of personal factors in employees of "comparison unit" and the firefighters of second group of joint unit

Factor	1st group of "comparison unit" (M ±m)	2nd group of "comparison unit" (M ±m)	1st group of joint unit (M ±m)	t (1 c.u., 2 joint unit)	t (2 c.u., 2 joint unit)
A	7,06 ±0,56	4,96 ±0,39	8,66 ±0,38	1,09	3,01**
B	5,58± 0,30	5,51± 0,33	6,94± 0,53	1,77	1,49
C	7,17 ±0,21	6,49 ±0,69	7,49 ±0,40	0,67	1,02
E	5,11 ±0,19	7,20 ±0,26	6,28 ±0,96	1,60	1,72
F	6,39 ±0,29	6,46± 0,44	6,02± 0,48	0,35	0,51
G	8,94± 0,33	7,86 ±0,30	7,06 ±0,32	1,44	0,70
H	5,76± 0,28	5,48 ±0,47	6,99 ±0,57	1,80	1,63
I	6,70± 0,65	4,66 ±0,48	5,66 ±0,40	1,79	1,44
L	3,89 ±0,21	5,08± 0,49	5,00± 0,49	2,67*	0,26
M	5,79 ±0,45	4,36± 0,27	4,77± 0,24	1,55	0,48
N	7,56 ±0,77	4,94 ±0,30	6,95 ±0,16	1,22	2,09*
O	5,27± 0,25	4,17 ±0,37	4,57 ±0,33	1,19	0,35
Q1	7,97± 0,41	5,30 ±0,41	5,54 ±0,42	1,89	0,33
Q2	4,31 ±0,67	5,06 ±0,54	5,46 ±0,45	1,28	1,66
Q3	8,15 ±0,78	5,36 ±0,37	6,46 ±0,47	2,12*	1,66
Q4	5,17 ±0,65	4,30± 0,29	4,35± 0,39	1,17	0,28

«*» – p < 0,05

When conducting a comparative analysis of expression of personal qualities among the second group of specialists firefighters "comparison unit" and the second group of joint unit received the following reliable differences. Specialists of fire-rescue unit SES of Ukraine, which belonged to the second group of joint unit are different compared to the firefighters of group 2 of "comparison unit" by a higher level of formation of the personal factor "A". That is, we can describe those firefighters as open for dialogue and interaction with other individuals. They usually attentive to others, are willing to work together.

We believe that it should be paid special attention for these aspects, as they directly determine the ability to work in team and psychological compatibility with other members of the joint unit. In addition, it was found that firefighters of second group of the joint unit, compared with the specialists of the first fire-rescue "comparison unit" differ by significantly higher level of

expression factor «L» ($t = 2,67$ at $p \leq 0,05$). These data show a distinct degree of formation in specialists in the second group of joint unit qualities such as openness, emotional attitude to the people, suppleness, and so on.

Table 6

Comparative characteristic expression of personal factors in employees of "comparison unit" and the firefighters of third group of joint unit

Factor	1st group of "comparison unit" (M ± m)	2nd group of "comparison unit" (M ± m)	3rd group of joint unit (M ± m)	t (1 c.u., 3 joint unit)	t (2 c.u., 3 joint unit)
A	7,06 ± 0,56	4,96 ± 0,39	5,95 ± 0,40	2,46*	1,74
B	5,58 ± 0,30	5,51 ± 0,33	6,74 ± 0,67	1,38	1,19
C	7,17 ± 0,21	6,49 ± 0,69	6,08 ± 0,26	1,51	0,32
E	5,11 ± 0,19	7,20 ± 0,26	6,39 ± 0,46	1,83	1,47
F	6,39 ± 0,29	6,46 ± 0,44	6,22 ± 0,17	0,50	0,39
G	8,94 ± 0,33	7,86 ± 0,30	7,59 ± 0,32	1,47	0,18
H	5,76 ± 0,28	5,48 ± 0,47	5,77 ± 0,26	0,15	0,52
I	6,70 ± 0,65	4,66 ± 0,48	4,85 ± 0,31	2,76*	0,56
L	3,89 ± 0,21	5,08 ± 0,49	6,70 ± 0,31	3,14**	1,78
M	5,79 ± 0,45	4,36 ± 0,27	4,44 ± 0,86	1,45	0,48
N	7,56 ± 0,77	4,94 ± 0,30	6,47 ± 0,43	1,12	2,05*
O	5,27 ± 0,25	4,17 ± 0,37	3,75 ± 0,35	2,17*	1,66
Q1	7,97 ± 0,41	5,30 ± 0,41	5,04 ± 0,37	2,11*	1,02
Q2	4,31 ± 0,67	5,06 ± 0,54	4,89 ± 0,32	0,56	1,04
Q3	8,15 ± 0,78	5,36 ± 0,37	5,48 ± 0,73	3,10**	0,55
Q4	5,17 ± 0,65	4,30 ± 0,29	4,97 ± 0,46	1,15	0,27

«*» – $p \leq 0,05$; «**» – $p \leq 0,01$

Also found that professionals-firefighters, which belong to the second group of the joint unit, differ by interpersonal ability to establish contacts and to demonstrate diplomacy and coldness at communication. Usually these professionals are emotionally restrained, cunning and can calculate in advance the situation ($t = 2,09$ $p \leq 0,05$ when compared to the 2nd unit).

In addition, one more major feature of firefighters who belong to the second group of joint unit is sufficiently high levels of self-control, which finds its expression in the purposefulness, strong will, the ability to control their emotional expression and behavior.

We note that all of the listed reliable differences allow characterize employees of firefighting units that joined the second group of joint unit as potentially psychologically compatible and effective professional specialists.

Further comparative analysis allowed to allocate more number of significant differences in the expression of personal factors specialist-firefighters that went into the first and second groups of "comparison unit" and firefighters 3rd group of of the joint unit.

Showed a reliable difference in the severity of such personal factors as "A" ($t = 2,46$ at $p \leq 0,05$ when compared to the 1st group of "comparison unit"), "I" ($t = 2,76$ at $p \leq 0,05$ compared to the 1st group of "comparison unit"), "O" ($t = 2,17$ at $p \leq 0,05$ when compared to the 1st group of "comparison unit").

The results allow to characterize the firefighters of the 3rd group of joint unit as not enough open to communication, distrustful and restrained personalities. At the same time, these firefighters are usually self-confident, practical and rational in their actions. Sometimes, such qualities of firefighters do not contribute to establishing close business relationships with members of the primary tactical fire-rescue unit, as their are the main features are coldness and calculation. They are not able to admit their mistakes and apologize.

It was also noted that the firefighters who entered the 3rd group of joint unit have personal factor «L» authentically higher ($t = 3,14$, $p \leq 0,01$) than in a group 1 of "comparison unit". These personalities differ by caution towards others, egocentricity, a tendency to irritability and so on.

Specialists of this group are usually not inclined to accept responsibility for their actions. Along with this, the firefighters from the 3rd group of joint unit, express authentically lower personal factor «Q1» ($t = 2,11$, $p \leq 0,05$).

This factor indicates that firefighters from 3rd group of joint unit are resistant against the rules and traditions. Sometimes it is very difficult for them to accept any changes and adapt to new conditions of life. In addition, firefighters of 3rd group of joint unit not differ sufficiently high level of self-control ($t = 3,10$, $p \leq 0,01$, compared with the 1st group of "comparison unit"), which may not positively reflected in the course of performance of their professional activities and on its final outcome.

Conclusions. Thus, summing up conducted research we note that in studying of individual-psychological characteristics of firefighters was established that on the formation of indicators of personal factors closest to the unit with high levels of psychological compatibility approached the specialists from the second group of the joint unit. Analysis of the expression of personality factors in the 1st and 3rd groups of joint unit proved the existence of obstacles to the formation of the cohesion of primary fire-rescue units SES of Ukraine in the form of subjective factors - personal qualities.

REFERENCES

1. Andreeva G.M. Obobshchenie i optimizacija sovmestnoj dejatel'nosti / G.M. Andreeva [i dr.]. — M.: Izd. MGU, 1897. — 301 s.
2. Bovin B.G. Osnovnye vidy dejatel'nosti i psihologicheskaja prigodnost' k sluzhbe v sisteme organov vnutrennih del [spravochnoe posobie] / pod red. Bovina B.G., Mjagkih N.I., Safronova A.D. — M., 1997 — 110 s.
3. Budnic'ka O.A. Individual'no-osobistisni determinanti emocijnih perezhivan' u psihotravmujucej situacii : avtoref. dis. na zdobuttja nauk. stupenja kand. psihol. nauk : spec. 19.00.09 «Psihologija dijatel'nosti v osoblivih umovah» / O.A. Budnic'ka. — K., 2001. — 14 s.
4. Gontarenko L.O. Profesiografichnij analiz dijatel'nosti pracivnikiv chergovo-dispechers'koї sluzhbi ekstremogo vikliku MNS Ukraїni : avtoref. dis. na zdobuttja nauk. stupenja kand. psihol. nauk: spec. 19.00.09 «Psihologija dijatel'nosti v osoblivih umovah» / L. O. Gontarenko. — Harkiv, 2008. — 22 s.
5. Derkach A.A., Zasykin, V.G. Professionalizm dejatel'nosti v osobyh i jekstremal'nyh uslovijah / A.A. Derkach, V.G. Zasykin // Psihologo-akmeologicheskije osnovy — M. : RAGS, 2003. — 156 s.
6. Derkach A. A. Professionalizm dejatel'nosti v osobyh i jekstremal'nyh uslovijah / A.A. Derkach. — M.: Izd. RAGS, 1998. — 223 s.
7. Dikaja L.G. Psihologicheskije problemy professional'noj dejatel'nosti / pod red. L.G. Dikoj, A.N. Zankovskogo. — M.: Nauka, 1991. — 166 s.
8. Cvsjukov O.P. Psihologichne prognozuvannja nadijnosti dijatel'nosti pracivnikiv avarijno-rjatuval'nih pidrozdiliv MNS Ukraїni: [monografija] / O. P. Cvsjukov, O. V. Timchenko. — Harkiv : UCZU, 2007. — 288 s.
9. Tsokota V.R. Psikhologichni osoblyvosti struktury reguljatornoi sfery viyskovykh pozhezhnykh strokovoi ta kontraktnoi sluzhby / V.S. Tsokota // Вісник ХННПУ імені Г.С. Сковороди. — №42. — Т.2. — КН.: ННПУ, 2013. — С. 196-203.

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